

1 First report of *Monalonion bondari* (Hemiptera: Miridae) as the causal agent of lateral
2 shoot dieback in *Eucalyptus* spp. in Brazil and its control strategies

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16 Abstract

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18 Lateral shoot dieback has emerged as a significant disorder affecting *Eucalyptus* spp.
19 plantations in Brazil, with increasing incidence and unclear etiology. During field
20 observations, plant bug species (Miridae) were consistently found in symptomatic
21 areas, raising the hypothesis of their involvement in the onset of the disease. This
22 study aimed to identify the insect species associated with dieback symptoms, evaluate
23 their ability to induce damage under controlled conditions, and test the efficacy of
24 insecticides for population control. Morphological and molecular analyses confirmed
25 the presence of *Monalonion bondari*, a mirid species previously reported as a pest in
26 cocoa (*Theobroma cacao*), now observed infesting young *Eucalyptus* trees.
27 Experimental infestations with *M. bondari* induced the characteristic shoot dieback
28 symptoms, similar to those observed in the field, confirming its role as the causal
29 agent. Furthermore, field trials demonstrated that applications of thiamethoxam and
30 bifenthrin significantly reduced the insect population, with protective effects for up
31 to 15 days post-application. These findings represent the first report of *M. bondari*
32 damaging eucalypt in Brazil and provide evidence-based strategies for its chemical
33 control. Implementing targeted monitoring and pest management can mitigate
34 damage and enhance plantation sustainability.

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36 **Keywords:** Eucalypt disease, sucking pest, integrated pest management.
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38 1 INTRODUCTION

39 Eucalypt is a tree of significant economic value in various regions worldwide,
40 including Brazil. However, the emergence of pests and diseases has been impacting
41 commercial plantations, leading to considerable crop losses (Wingfield et al. 2008). A
42 recently identified and severe disease, initially attributed to *Pseudoplagiostoma eucalypti*
43 (Fungi: Ascomycota: Pseudoplagiostomataceae), has been affecting plantations across
44 several Brazilian states (Zauza et al. 2023). Typical symptoms of the disease include leaf
45 spots, branch cankers, shoot blight, defoliation, and dieback (Zauza et al. 2023). These
46 symptoms have been observed in nearly all hybrid clones of *Eucalyptus* spp.

47 Although Zauza et al. (2023) demonstrated that *P. eucalypti* can cause lateral shoot
48 die-back under high humidity conditions (relative humidity above 90%), this fungus, as
49 an endophyte often co-occurring with other pathogens, typically plays a secondary role
50 in disease development (Crous et al. 2019). Therefore, it is unlikely to cause significant
51 damage in a short time frame. In February 2023, during a field trip to Eucalyptus
52 plantations located in southern Bahia State, several plants were observed exhibiting
53 symptoms of lateral shoot dieback, including petiole necrosis, excessive sprouting, and
54 lesions along the leaf veins (Figure 1). Eggs and adult plant bugs (Hemiptera: Miridae)
55 were frequently observed in association with the affected tissues (Figure 1G).

56 This observation has led to the question whether these insects could be associated
57 with or if potentially could cause this disease-like symptoms. Plant-bugs are known to
58 cause severe damages in several crops (Muhamad and Way 1995; Montilla Pérez et al.
59 2014; Roy et al. 2015; Kodakkadan et al. 2020). In Indonesia, for example, the species
60 *Helopeltis theivora* and *H. bradyi* (Heteroptera: Miridae) have been reported to cause
61 widespread damage in eucalyptus plantations. The typical symptoms include lateral shoot
62 dieback, leaf curling, deformation, and tissue drying (Kodakkadan et al. 2020). In Brazil,
63 plant-bugs have not yet been reported as causing diseases in eucalypt trees. However,
64 cocoa (*Theobroma cacao* L.: Malvaceae) plantations in Bahia, a major cocoa-producing
65 region of Brazil, are affected by damage caused by *Monalonion bondari* Costa Lima
66 1938, a Miridae species. In cocoa, feeding by these insects induces necrotic lesions on
67 fruits and shoot dieback in young tissues due the toxic action of their salivary secretions,
68 leading to significant physiological stress and yield losses in cocoa plantations. Given the
69 severity of the damage and the pest's capacity to cause persistent injury to economically

70 important crops, effective management strategies are required to reduce insect population
71 levels and minimize productivity losses.

72 Chemical control has been the predominant method for managing insects in the
73 Miridae family, particularly for species that cause damage to crops (Rahib Chowdhury et
74 al. 2013; Zhang et al. 2015; Dumont and Provost 2019). Among the most effective
75 insecticides are molecules such as thiamethoxam and bifenthrin, which have shown
76 efficiency in controlling *Helopeltis theivora*, a major pest in tea crops (Rahib Chowdhury
77 et al. 2013; Zhang et al. 2015). Their success in tea plantations highlights their potential
78 application for managing these pests in other crops. These insecticides are expected to be
79 effective to significantly reduce insect populations in eucalypt plantations.

80 The objectives of this study were to identify the insect species associated with the
81 symptoms observed in eucalyptus plantations in southern Bahia, where eggs and adult
82 plant bugs (Miridae) were found near the lesions; to determine whether feeding by this
83 insect induces the same symptoms observed under field conditions and to evaluate the
84 effectiveness of insecticides for its control.

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Figure 1: Symptoms of lateral shoot dieback in eucalyptus plantations where eggs and adult plant bugs (Miridae) were found near the lesions: A- Affected trees; B- Detail of lateral shoot dieback of a single tree; C – Minicankers and secondary shoot emergence (arrow) at the insect feeding site; D- Dark lesions at the

90 point of insect attack; E – Generalized dieback in a severely affected tree. F- Lesions on the main leaf vein;
91 G – Detail of the adult insect and eggs (arrow) on the plant tissue.

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94 **2 MATERIAL AND METHODS**

95 ***Study area and field observations***

96 Field inspections were conducted in February 2023 in Eucalyptus plantations
97 located in southern Bahia State, Brazil. During these inspections, plants exhibiting
98 symptoms of lateral shoot dieback, characterized by petiole necrosis, excessive sprouting,
99 and lesions along the leaf veins were identified. Eggs and adult plant bugs (Hemiptera:
100 Miridae) were frequently observed in association with the affected tissues. The
101 distribution indicates that the affected plantations encompass approximately 19,000 ha in
102 southern Bahia, highlighting both the occurrence of symptomatic areas and the locations
103 where insect specimens were collected (Figure 2)

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105 ***Morphological and Molecular Identification***

106 Thirty insect specimens were collected from eucalyptus plantations exhibiting
107 lateral shoot dieback symptoms in areas of southern of Bahia where insect infestation was
108 recorded. These specimens were carefully preserved in 90% ethanol to maintain their
109 integrity for morphological and molecular identification.

110 Morphological identification was based on external morphology and male
111 genitalia under stereomicroscopy. The body size, shape and color, head and eyes
112 morphology, labium length, antennal segmentation and coloration, pronotum and
113 hemelytral color patterns and leg pigmentation, were analyzed as described by Carvalho
114 (1972) and Gamboa et al. (2020). The specimens were examined by Prof. Paulo Fiuza.
115 from Department of Animal Biology at the Universidade Federal de Viçosa.

116
 117 Figure 2: Distribution of *Eucalyptus* plantations exhibiting lateral shoot dieback in southern Bahia State,
 118 where adult plant bugs specimens were observed.
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120 For molecular identification, a total genomic DNA was extracted from five insect
 121 specimens preserved in 90% ethanol using the Wizard® Genomic DNA Purification Kit
 122 (Promega) following the manufacturer's instructions.

123 The cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) gene fragment was amplified by
 124 polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using the universal primers LCO1490 (5'
 125 GGTCAACAAATCATAAAGATATTGG 3') and HCO2198 (5'
 126 TAAACTTCAGGGTGACCAAAAATCA 3') (Folmer et al., 1994). The PCR was
 127 performed in a total of 25 μL containing 3 μL genomic DNA (gDNA), 10.7 μL MilliQ-
 128 H_2O , 2.5 μL 10X PCR Buffer Mg^{2+} free (Sinapse Inc) 2.0 μL MgCl_2 (25 mM) (Sinapse
 129 Inc), 2.0 μL dNTP (2.5 mM) (Sinapse Inc), 2 μL of each primer (5 μM), and 0.3 μL Taq
 130 DNA Polymerase (5 U μL^{-1}) (Sinapse Inc). The PCR amplification conditions used were
 131 94 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 min for primary denaturation, then 35 cycles at 94 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 s, 53 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 45
 132 s, 72 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 min, with a final extension at 72 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min. PCR amplicons were
 133 visualized under ultraviolet light after electrophoresis using 5 μL amplicon in 1.5%
 134 (w v^{-1}) agarose gel stained with SYBR Safe (Life Technologies). The subsequent
 135 purification process was performed using a mix of Exo-Sap (Exonuclease/Alkaline
 136 Phosphatase) (Cellco Biotech). The bidirectional sequencing was performed by the

137 Sanger method using the same PCR primers at the Molecular Biology Laboratory
138 CEBTEC at ESALQ, University of São Paulo.

139 Consensus COI sequences were compared with those deposited in GenBank using
140 BLASTn (NCBI). Species identification was determined based on the highest sequence
141 similarity and query coverage with reference sequences.

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143 ***Induction of symptoms***

144 Three insect specimens at different developmental stages (1 adult and 2 nymphs),
145 collected from the field, were taken to the Forest Health laboratory at Veracel Pulp
146 Company (Eunápolis, Bahia) for further analysis. The insects were then introduced into
147 an entomological cage containing five healthy, 3-month-old rooted cuttings of *Eucalyptus*
148 *urophylla* x *Eucalyptus grandis* (clone 2123). These saplings were chosen to represent
149 young, healthy plants for monitoring potential damage. To ensure accurate results,
150 another set of five samplings from the same clone was placed outside the cage, completely
151 separated from the insects to prevent any contact. The plants maintained inside the cage
152 were inspected daily to evaluate the development of dieback symptoms, including the
153 presence of necrotic lesions, cankers, and other visible symptoms or injury.

154 ***Effect of insecticides for insect control***

155 A plot of 4-month-old of *E. urophylla* x *E. grandis* (clone 2123) with severe
156 dieback symptoms was selected. The plot was divided into three blocks containing 10
157 planting rows. In each block, 20 plants were randomly selected to be sampled in order to
158 evaluate the initial insect infestation.

159 Prior to insecticide application, the number of insects present on each plant was
160 counted (Census). Subsequently, treatments were applied according to the manufacturer's
161 recommendations. The experimental design consisted of three treatments: thiamethoxam
162 applied at 200 mL per 100 L of water with a spray volume of 200 L ha⁻¹; bifenthrin applied
163 at 300 g per 100 L of water with a spray volume of 200 L ha⁻¹; and an untreated control.

164 To evaluate treatment effectiveness, the number of the insects present on the plants
165 were recorded at 1, 7 and 15 days after insecticide spraying.

166 An untreated control group was maintained without insecticide application to
167 account for natural fluctuations in insect population and to ensure that any observed

168 reduction in insect numbers was due to the insecticide spraying rather than to natural
169 mortality or dispersal.

170 A generalized linear model of quasipoisson (GLM) was used to investigate the
171 effect of treatments and time (days) after spraying on the reduction of the insect number
172 in each block. The selection of the best model was based on the lowest AIC value among
173 the models. The quality of the GLMs was evaluated by checking the normality of the
174 model's residual distribution through a Q-Q plot and plotting the model's residuals against
175 the fitted values to verify their homoscedasticity. All analyses were performed, and
176 graphics generated with R 3.4.1 (R Core Team 2023). The package multcomp (Hothorn
177 et al. 2008) for the multiple comparison analysis, and the package MuMIn (Barton 2018)
178 were used to select a model through AIC.

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180 **3 RESULTS**

181 *Morphological and Molecular Identification*

182 Based on morphological characteristics, the examined specimens were identified
183 as belonging to *Monalonion bondari*.

184 Adults exhibited an elongated, shiny body (>8 mm), with the head wider than long
185 and eyes occupying most of the anterior region. The posterior portion of the head tapered
186 toward the thorax, forming a short neck. The labium did not reach the middle coxae.
187 Antennal segment I was pear-shaped and shorter than the head, whereas segments II–IV
188 were filiform; the antennae were as long as or longer than the body, extending to the
189 membrane apex. The hemelytra fully covered the abdomen, and the membrane contained
190 a single, elongate cell. Tarsi bore large, fleshy, divergent pseudopulvilli.

191 Coloration was predominantly dark brown with a reddish abdomen. The pronotum was
192 black with three lighter (reddish-brown) bands, and the scutellum was black with a pale
193 longitudinal stripe. Hemelytra were dark with pale spots at the base of the clavus and
194 embolium; the cuneus and membrane veins ranged from dark brown to reddish, and the
195 membrane was distinctly infuscated.

196 In males, antennal segment I was globose and lighter basally, and segment III was
197 cylindrical, with diameter equal to or smaller than segment II. The hind femora lacked a
198 white ring or stripe, were medially tapered, and uniformly light-colored, sometimes
199 darker at the base or apex. The fore and mid tibiae were predominantly pale, whereas the
200 hind tibiae were dark. Male genitalia showed a left paramere enlarged medially and

201 tapering to a pointed lobe, and a narrow right paramere with a median sinuosity and blunt
202 apex.

203 To proceed the molecular identification, forward and reverse reads were
204 assembled to generate consensus COI barcode sequences following standard procedures..
205 After trimming and editing, a final consensus length of 685 pb was obtained, and no
206 evidence of NumtS was detected. The five sequences of *M. bondari* resulted in four
207 haplotypes (NCBI accession numbers H1: OR961527; H2: OR961528; H3: OR961529;
208 H4: OR961530; H4: OR961531). BLAST searches against the NCBI GenBank
209 nucleotide database showed that the *M. bondari* sequences shared more than 98% identity
210 among themselves. The closest specie to *M. bondari* was *Monalonion velezangeli*
211 (Sequence ID PQ046645.1), with 89% sequence identity.

212 This study represents the first molecular records of *Monalonion bondari* deposited
213 in GenBank and provides a reference for future studies.

214 ***Induction of symptoms***

215 At 24 h of the introduction of the insects into the cage (Figure 3 A), all plants
216 expressed dieback symptoms (Figure 3 B and C) as observed in the field and as described
217 by Zauza et al. (2023). Differently, plants outside the cage remained healthy, without any
218 symptoms. After five days of exposure, all plants showed dryness in all apical young
219 shoots (Figure 3C). Those insects introduced into the cage successfully inserted their
220 stylets into the plants, indicating active feeding behavior, and females deposited eggs
221 within the tissues (Figure 3B). Such feeding activity may result not only in mechanical
222 damage but also in physiological alterations caused by the injection of salivary toxins,
223 which can induce disease-like symptoms such as necrosis and shoot dieback, even in the
224 absence of pathogen transmission.

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Figure 3: Reproduction of symptoms caused by *Monalonion bondari* on a hybrid clone of *Eucalyptus grandis* × *E. urophylla* under controlled conditions. A – Cage containing healthy plants exposed to insect attack. B – Insect feeding on a rooted eucalypt cutting by inserting its stylets. C – Evolution of disease symptoms at 1, 3, and 5 days, respectively, after the introduction of the insects into the cage. D - Lesions along petiole and main leaf vein after 7 days.

233 ***Effect of insecticides for insect control***

234 After spraying, insect abundance was lower than at day 0 (census) and remained
235 lower than in the control treatment at all post-application evaluation times (Figure 4).
236 Thiamethoxam and bifenthrin were equally effective, with no significant difference
237 between them, and both reduced insect abundance relative to the census and control
238 treatments.

239 Figure 4: Number of *Monalonia bondari* insects found in eucalypt plants in each treatment over 1 (A), 7
240 (B) and 15 (C) days after spraying the insecticides. In (A), (B) and (C) the bars bearing the same letters
241 indicate similar values at the 5% significance level (Tukey post-hoc test). The lines within the boxplots
242 represent the median, the lower and upper boundaries of the boxes represent, respectively, the 25th and
243 75th percentiles, while the whiskers extend to the smallest and largest values within 1.5 box lengths. The
244 dots represent the outliers.
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247 **4 DISCUSSION**

248 This study demonstrates that *Monalonia bondari* is the causal agent of the lateral
249 shoot dieback observed in *Eucalyptus* spp. in southern Bahia, Brazil. Morphological and
250 molecular analyses consistently identified the specimens as *M. bondari*, and the COI
251 sequences generated here represent the first molecular records of this species deposited
252 in GenBank. The taxonomic identity of the insect is also consistent with its known
253 biogeographic and host-association patterns. Based on the morphological characters and
254 molecular analyses, the specimens examined here were assigned to the tribe Monaloniini,
255 genus *Monalonia*, a lineage endemic to the Neotropics (Carvalho 1972; Cassis and
256 Schuh 2012; Gamboa et al. 2020). Within this genus, *M. bondari* is an endemic mirid
257 species from Bahia that has been recognized as a pest of cocoa (*Theobroma cacao*)
258 plantations, where feeding on young shoots, flowers and pods can result in substantial
259 yield losses due to necrosis, branch dieback, and pod scarring (Muhamad and Way 1995;
260 Sánchez, 2011; Moubarak et al. 2022). This association is epidemiologically relevant

261 because southern Bahia contains extensive cocoa-growing areas that occur near
262 eucalyptus plantations

263 In the present study, cocoa plantations are situated near the sites where *M. bondari*
264 was collected in *Eucalyptus* spp. plantations, suggesting that the regional abundance of
265 suitable host plants may have facilitated its occurrence on Eucalyptus. Symptoms
266 expression became more prominent after periods of heavy rainfall, which is when the
267 symptoms typically emerge (Wu et al. 2002; Demirel 2022;). Increased rainfall tends to
268 boost the population of *Monalonia* and increase mirid activity.

269 The causal role of *M. bondari* is biologically consistent with previous reports of
270 other *Monalonia* species, including *M. velezangeli*, *M. annulipes* and *M. dissimulatum*,
271 causing similar symptoms on *Theobroma grandiflorum*, *Coffea arabica*, *Persea*
272 *americana* and *Persea gratissima* (Santos & Stracieri, 2025; Roy et al. 2015). In
273 Eucalyptus, comparable symptoms have been described for *M. velezangeli* in Colombia
274 and for *Helopeltis bradyi* and *H. theivora* in Indonesia, where mirid feeding induces rapid
275 necrosis, shoot dieback, deformation, leaf drying and loss of apical dominance (Rodas et
276 al., 2014; Kodakkadan et al., 2020; Srikumar et al., 2021). These reports reinforce our
277 observation that the disease-like symptoms observed in southern Bahia can arise
278 primarily from mirid feeding rather than from *Pseudoplagiostoma eucalypti* alone, as
279 previously reported by Zauza et al. (2023). However, feeding damage may predispose
280 host tissues to secondary fungal colonization, including by *P. eucalypti*, thereby
281 increasing symptom severity and complicating field diagnosis. In this context, secondary
282 fungal infection may intensify tissue necrosis, blight and shoot dieback. Similar post-
283 injury colonization by *Neofusicoccum ribis* and other Botryosphaeriaceae has also been
284 reported in *Eucalyptus* spp. following damage caused by *Monalonia velezangeli* and
285 *Helopeltis* spp. (Rodas et al., 2009, 2014; Jami et al., 2022), reinforcing that secondary
286 fungal colonization may obscure the primary cause of the disorder.

287 Although these observations support mirid feeding as the primary trigger of
288 symptom development, the mechanistic relationship between insect injury and
289 subsequent fungal colonization remains unclear. It is well established that mirids inject
290 toxin saliva that leads to tissue death (Sarker and Mukhopadhyay 2006; Kodakkadan et
291 al. 2020), but it is still unclear whether fungal infection exacerbates the symptoms
292 initiated by feeding damage. Further studies are therefore needed to clarify the interaction
293 between these organisms and to define their relative contributions to the onset and
294 progression of dieback in Eucalyptus plantations.

295 Despite this unresolved interaction, our results clearly indicate that *M. bondari* is
296 the primary target for management in this pathosystem. Both bifenthrin and thiamethoxam
297 proved effective in controlling *M. bondari*, as expected. This efficacy aligns with previous
298 observations where these insecticides have demonstrated successful control of other
299 insects within the same genus (Zhang et al. 2015; Dumont and Provost 2019;
300 Amarasekare and Shearer 2020). Previous studies have reported an efficiency of 86% to
301 90% in controlling *Monalonion velezangeli* and *Helopeltis theivora* using the same
302 insecticides, bifenthrin and thiamethoxam. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of
303 these chemical treatments in managing these mirid pests, as observed by Montilla Pérez
304 et al. (2014) and Rahib Chowdhury et al. (2013). Both studies highlighted the ability of
305 these insecticides to significantly reduce pest populations, providing valuable insights for
306 the control of similar pests, such as *M. bondari*, in different agricultural crops. Broad-
307 spectrum insecticides reduce pest populations and prevent reinfestation for up to 15 days
308 after application. As previously reported for other species of plant-bugs, chemical
309 insecticides lose efficacy over time, with their effectiveness halving 17 days after
310 application (Amarasekare and Shearer 2020). In the present study, however, we did not
311 observe any reinfestation within the 15-day period following insecticide spraying. This is
312 advantageous because the eggs of *M. bondari* are laid inside the branches of eucalypt
313 trees, which prevents direct contact with the insecticide. However, even after the eggs
314 hatch, the insect can still be affected due to the broad-spectrum activity of the insecticides,
315 which target various stages of insect development. This makes them suitable for
316 managing *M. bondari* infestations in eucalypt plantations.

317 Although this study identifies *M. bondari* as the primary causal agent of lateral
318 shoot dieback and demonstrates that its populations can be effectively suppressed with
319 insecticides, further work is needed to support sustainable management of this emerging
320 pest.

321 AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

322 **Rafael Ferreira Alfenas:** Conceptualization, investigation, methodology, data curation,
323 visualization, writing – original draft, review, and editing. **Jessica Josefa Sanches:**
324 Investigation, methodology, processing datasets, data curation, visualization, writing –
325 original draft, review, and editing. **Acelino Couto Alfenas:** Investigation, supervision,
326 writing – original draft, review, and editing. **Nilmara Pereira Caires:** Methodology,
327 visualization of data, writing – review and editing. **Frederico Nanini:** Methodology,

328 writing - original draft, review, and editing. **Cristiano Feldens Schwertner:**
329 Methodology, writing - original draft, review, and editing. **Maurício Magalhães**
330 **Domingues:** Methodology, visualization of data, writing – review and editing. **Taís**
331 **Aparecida Machado dos Santos:** Preparation and editing of figures, visual
332 representation of data, writing – review and editing.

333

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343 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

344 The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author
345 upon request and can also be accessed via the Zenodo public repository at the following
346 link <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17262446>

347

348 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT**

349 On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of
350 interest.

351

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